

Restore4Life

RESTORING WETLANDS
FOR A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

D1.1 WETLAND RESTORATION WIKI

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D1.1 WETLAND RESTORATION WIKI

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Abstract	This report investigates the success factors of wetland restoration by synthesizing systematic literature review findings, thematic analysis, and expert opinions. It provides a comprehensive understanding of the ecological, societal, governance, functional, climate adaptation, adaptive management, financial, and communication elements essential for successful wetland restoration. The findings inform a survey and data collection on European wetland restoration projects for the Restore4Life project. The insights will support the development of an online platform and Decision Support System (DSS) to identify, assess, and enhance wetland restoration efforts in the Danube Basin, promoting sustainable ecological health, societal well-being, and climate resilience.
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents an extensive examination of wetland restoration success factors, synthesizing findings from a systematic literature review combined with a thematic analysis and expert opinion. The study aims to provide a holistic understanding of the diverse elements contributing to successful wetland restoration projects, encompassing ecological, societal, governance, functional, climate adaptation, adaptive management, financial, and communication perspectives. The results are used to inform a survey and gather data on European wetland restoration projects from the Restore4Life project partners.

The concepts included in this report will serve as the basis for developing an online platform to support wetland restoration efforts in the Danube Basin. This platform will integrate existing datasets and maps to support the development of tools for identifying areas suitable for restoration. This initiative will also allow the creation of a comprehensive Decision Support System (DSS) for wetland restoration projects. The DSS will focus on the following objectives:

- 1 Identifying Wetland Areas:** Locating existing wetlands, former wetlands, and potential sites for future wetland restoration.
- 2 Assessing Restoration Success:** Supplying data to evaluate the success of wetland restoration efforts.
- 3 Future Services Development:** Providing data that can be utilized to create new services related to wetland restoration in the future.

The future web platform will allow the knowledge integration to inform decision-making processes. The platform is built upon a conceptual framework for integrating wetland restoration success factors (Task 1.1) and combines a Wetland Restoration Wiki and a Decision Support System (DSS) (Task 1.2). By synthesizing scientific knowledge, practical expertise, and advanced technologies, it transforms data into actionable restoration solutions. The DSS integrates a series of tools, including Citizen Science, Business Tools, AI/ML models, GIS-based analytics, and economic valuation methods, ensuring a holistic approach to wetland restoration.

Additionally, the platform will integrate the **Wetland4Life web app** for citizen science, allowing users to provide data about wetlands and rate their status using **CS observations and Remote Sensing algorithms (Task 2.2)**. The **Solution4Life app** will support stakeholders in **identifying and negotiating solutions** for wetland restoration. The platform will also **map existing citizen science projects** focused on biodiversity and the impact of pollution, fragmentation, and land-use change, integrating data from initiatives such as **eu.citizen.science and cs.observatories**.

The platform will also enable automatic ingestion and data integration from Copernicus services, in situ monitoring, and climate models (Task 1.1), powering the Wetland Restoration Decision Support System (Task 1.2). This system provides a structured decision-making approach by integrating key components of the general architecture, with multiple components, each playing a specific role in data ingestion, processing, and visualization.

General Architecture

1. Data Layer (Ingestion and Storage)
2. Processing and Analysis Layer (AI/ML & GIS)
3. User Interface Layer (Visualization and Interaction)
Additional Components
4. Stakeholder & Policy Dashboard (Monitoring Restoration Progress)
5. Citizen Science Zone (Monitoring Tools for the Public)
6. Business Zone (Ecosystem Services & Wetland Economy)
7. Learning & Communication Hub (Environmental Education & Water Literacy)

The **Learning & Communication Hub** will include **environmental education and water literacy tools** developed under **Task 2.3**. These tools will feature interactive **learning experiences**, including the **Blue-Green Space 4 All game**, workshops, and **school-based wetland experiential learning programs ('Wetland Goes Local')**. Additionally, the platform will provide tools for comparing **historical maps with present field conditions**, enabling users to assess wetland restoration success over time. This comprehensive integration ensures that decision-makers and practitioners receive optimal solutions tailored to ecological, social, and climate adaptation needs. The platform builds links with other restoration initiatives (Task 1.3) and facilitates co-created roadmaps and action plans (Task 1.4). It serves as a dynamic space where policymakers, researchers, NGOs, and citizens can access: **Real-time data and predictive models** for wetland monitoring and forecasting. **Knowledge-sharing tools** through the Wetland Restoration Wiki, enabling cross-sectoral learning. **Interactive dashboards** for stakeholders to visualize progress in wetland restoration. **Integrated decision-making processes**, ensuring alignment with **EU Nature Restoration Law, the Biodiversity Strategy 2030, and national policies**.

By combining science, policy, business, and community engagement, the platform accelerates wetland restoration efforts and maximizes their ecological, social, and economic impact.

Several success perspectives were identified that, once addressed, may enhance the positive impacts of wetland restoration efforts on ecological health, societal well-being, and climate resilience, ultimately leading to more effective and sustainable restoration projects. Most of these factors are linked with the need to better incorporate the Ecosystem Service (ES) approach into assessing the success of wetland restoration. The implementation of this holistic understanding of success factors will be used to assess the restoration success of the future projects mostly on long term on several perspectives and not only on the ecological and functional perspectives but rather from a larger social, business and governance perspective

- **Ecological and functional perspective.** Success is linked to achieving functional goals, such as improved water quality, increased biodiversity, and overall ecological health. Key indicators include the diversity and provision of (mainly regulating) ecosystem services and ecosystem resilience to climate stressors.
- **Societal and community engagement perspective.** Active community involvement, integration of local knowledge, education, and capacity building are crucial for success.

Indicators include the level of community participation, integration of traditional knowledge, and long-term community stewardship.

- **Governance and policy perspective.** Supportive governance structures, clear regulatory frameworks, and multi-stakeholder collaborations are essential. Success factors include policy alignment, regulatory clarity, property rights and effective coordination mechanisms.
- **Adaptive management and monitoring perspective.** The ability to adjust restoration approaches based on continuous monitoring and feedback enhances project resilience. Indicators include the implementation of adaptive management strategies and the continuity of post-restoration monitoring.
- **Communication and outreach perspective.** Effective communication and public awareness initiatives are vital for engaging stakeholders and fostering community support. Success is measured by the reach and engagement of advocacy campaigns and public perceptions of the restored wetland.
- **Financial and business support perspective.** Sustainable funding mechanisms and business sector engagement are critical for long-term restoration success. Indicators include the diversity of funding sources, business partnerships, and the economic impact of restoration projects.
- **Climate adaptation perspective.** Incorporating climate change projections and resilience strategies into restoration planning is crucial. Success factors include the presence of adaptive strategies and flexibility in management plans to address climate impacts.

The study underscores the complexity of wetland restoration efforts and the importance of having a multifaceted approach in evaluating success. The findings highlight the interdependence of ecological health, societal well-being, and effective governance. By integrating these dimensions, future restoration projects can be more effectively planned, implemented, and evaluated.

The next steps involve enhancing knowledge exchange among scientists, practitioners and policymakers by developing, improving and populating the Wetland Restoration online platform. Assessing the success of restoration projects requires consideration of multiple spatial scales (from regional to local) and long-time perspectives. This approach ensures that the evaluation of restoration success is relevant and comprehensive and contributes to more sustainable wetland restoration initiatives.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Wetlands, as dynamic ecosystems, play a pivotal role in maintaining ecological balance, supporting biodiversity, and providing a myriad of ecosystem services essential for human well-being (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005; Villa & Bernal, 2018).

Wetlands sustain critical ecological processes that deliver essential ecosystem services, such as water storage and aquifer recharge, water quality regulation, assimilation of pollutants and excess nutrients, sediment deposition, and long-term carbon sequestration (Costanza et al., 2014). In Europe, the most significant wetland habitats for carbon storage include well-functioning salt marshes, healthy mires, peatlands (bogs and fens), and riparian, fluvial, and swamp forests.

Over the last three centuries, an estimated 87% of wetland ecosystems have been eradicated globally, with much of this loss occurring in inland regions. Land-use change, driven by agricultural expansion, urban development and industrial activities, has been identified as the main driver contributing to the degradation of inland wetlands and their biodiversity (Silva et al., 2007). Another significant driver of wetland loss is river regulation, which has been influenced by inland navigation, hydropower developments, land reclamation, and hydrotechnical constructions primarily aimed at flood protection. Recent data indicate an accelerated decline in coastal wetlands, which have diminished by 31% from 1970 to 2008 (WWF, 2019). This alarming trend underscores the urgent need for effective wetland restoration initiatives.

Recognising the critical importance of wetlands and wetland restoration, the Restore4Life project has embarked on a journey to understand and catalogue the critical success factors contributing to the effectiveness and long-term sustainability of wetland restoration initiatives in Europe. This project aims to bridge the gap between theoretical research and practical application, ensuring that restoration efforts are informed by the latest scientific insights and best practices.

Ecological restoration has been defined in various ways, from focusing strictly on the improvement of the ecological state of a degraded area to incorporating human factors that can either aid or hinder the restoration process. The Society of Ecological Restoration (SER 2004) defines restoration as the intentional activity that initiates or accelerates the recovery of an ecosystem with respect to its health, integrity, and sustainability, focusing on restoring critical functions and characteristics like soil properties, water chemistry, biotic composition, and hydrological dynamics.

Early definitions often focused on applying scientific data to restore ecosystems perceived as degraded, damaged or destroyed (SER, 2004), aiming to return them to a functional state existing before anthropogenic degradation. Success was deemed achieved if a functioning ecosystem was restored according to specific restoration goals (Kentula, 2000). However, this approach has evolved to recognize the need for a more holistic understanding of ecosystems, acknowledging the impact of human activities on the restoration process.

Modern approaches to ecological restoration emphasize the creation of robust, self-supporting systems (Ruiz-Jaen and Aide, 2005) or healthy, self-sustaining systems (Palmer et al., 2005). These approaches recognize that restoration is not merely about returning an ecosystem to a previous state but about creating resilient systems capable of adapting to changing conditions. This broader understanding has led to definitions that consider restoration as the process of restoring one or more valued processes or attributes of a landscape (Davis and Slobodkin, 2004).

While scientific data may indicate that a site is degraded and needs restoration, deciding how, to what state, and by whom is inherently a human endeavour. Restoration goals are often based on shared values, which can be social, environmental, economic, cultural, moral, political, or religious. Successful restoration should therefore provide ecosystem services that people value (Martin, 2017), making it a collaborative endeavour that transcends disciplinary boundaries (Nilsson et al. 2019). Given that restoration is context-specific, it is vital to learn from past experiences and transfer that knowledge while establishing general principles. Palmer et al. (2005) proposed five principles: i) having a guiding image of a dynamic state, ii) improving ecosystems, iii) increasing resilience, iv) causing no lasting harm, and v) completing ecological assessments. Successful restoration also contributes to scientific knowledge and management practices.

Recognizing the numerous human factors involved, some authors have proposed more comprehensive definitions: "Ecological restoration is the total set of ideas and practices (social, scientific, economic, political) involved in the restoration of ecosystems" (Hobbs, 2004). Hence, it is essential to consider human aspects (Shackelford et al., 2013; Wortley, Hero, and Howes, 2013). Ecological restoration involves multiple actors working at various levels and scales with differing interests, creating dynamic governance contexts (Richardson and Lefroy, 2013). The restoration process may positively or negatively impact these actors' interests, and their awareness of the restoration outcomes can influence their involvement and cooperation (Palmer et al., 2005).

The UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration offers a broad definition: "Ecosystem restoration means assisting in the recovery of ecosystems that have been degraded or destroyed, as well as conserving the ecosystems that are still intact. Healthier ecosystems, with richer biodiversity, yield greater benefits such as more fertile soils, bigger yields of timber and fish, and larger stores of greenhouse gases. Restoring ecosystems large and small protects and improves the livelihoods of people who depend on them. It also helps to regulate disease and reduce the risk of natural disasters" (Dudley et al., 2021)

Figure 1. Four major categories of restoration activities along the restorative continuum (from Nelson et al., 2024)

The goal of wetland restoration is to emulate a self-regulating natural system that is ecologically integrated into the landscape (see Figure 1). Wetland restoration can provide multiple benefits, including biodiversity conservation, climate change adaptation, and human well-being. These benefits can be collective and individual, impacting personal, ecological, cultural, and socio-economic values. The type of restoration chosen for each site depends on the current state of the wetlands, the desired reference state, and potential management options.

Wetland restoration, categorized as a nature-based solution (NbS), leverages the power of nature to address various socio-environmental challenges and enhance human well-being (Rey Benayas et al. 2009). Wetland restoration stands out as a prominent NbS, addressing environmental challenges while simultaneously providing ecological and societal benefits. Wetlands contribute to biodiversity conservation, water purification, and climate change mitigation, to name just a few of the benefits these ecosystems provide. Wetland restoration involves rehabilitating degraded or drained areas, often through reestablishing natural hydrological patterns, planting native vegetation, and removing invasive species. By doing so, wetland restoration enhances the resilience of ecosystems, promotes water retention, and mitigates the impacts of flooding by acting as natural sponges that absorb and slowly release excess water. Moreover, these restored wetlands serve as critical habitats for diverse plant and animal species, fostering biodiversity and supporting the life cycles of numerous organisms. From a climate perspective, wetlands sequester carbon, helping to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions. Importantly, wetland restoration projects often engage local communities, providing opportunities for sustainable livelihoods, recreational activities, and educational opportunities. As a multifaceted nature-based solution, wetland restoration exemplifies the potential for harmonizing human activities with the environment, offering both immediate and long-term benefits for ecological integrity and human well-being.

Importantly, wetland restoration projects often engage local communities, providing opportunities for sustainable livelihoods, recreational activities, and educational

opportunities. Engaging with human communities is paramount to sustaining ecological restoration efforts (Higgs 2003; Hallett et al. 2013). However, the literature indicates a lack of quantification regarding the social values of restoration actions (Evju et al. 2020). Wetland restoration exemplifies the potential for harmonizing human activities with the environment, offering both immediate and long-term benefits for ecological integrity and human well-being.

Wetland restoration is not a static process; it is an evolving and adaptive journey requiring a transdisciplinary approach. The Restore4Life project recognises the dynamic interplay of various factors and their interconnectedness within the wetland restoration landscape. By adopting a transdisciplinary approach through collaborative efforts between practitioners and researchers, the project aims to fill the gap in understanding wetland restoration success factors.

One of the primary objectives of Restore4Life is to develop a Wetland Restoration Wiki as a dynamic and collaborative platform. This Wiki will serve as a structured resource for policymakers, practitioners, local communities, and scientists. It will facilitate knowledge exchange and experience sharing among stakeholders, providing a comprehensive repository of information and best practices. This collaborative platform will help enhance future wetland restoration endeavours, ensuring that restoration efforts are informed by the latest insights and perspectives.

In conclusion, wetlands are invaluable ecosystems that provide essential services for both the environment and human well-being. The degradation and loss of wetlands highlight the urgent need for effective restoration efforts. The Restore4Life project aims to contribute to this goal by identifying and cataloguing the critical success factors for wetland restoration in Europe. By adopting a holistic, transdisciplinary approach and engaging with local communities, Restore4Life seeks to enhance the effectiveness and sustainability of wetland restoration initiatives. The development of a Wetland Restoration Wiki will further support these efforts, providing a dynamic platform for knowledge exchange and collaboration.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

In our quest to identify wetland restoration success factors, we conducted a systematic literature review on wetland restoration utilising the SCOPUS database as a main source to identify peer-reviewed papers dealing with wetland restoration success.

We established clear eligibility criteria for scientific publications:

- **Inclusion Criteria.** We considered scientific publications in the form of review papers. The selected literature had to be available in English and primarily focus on wetland restoration.
- **Exclusion Criteria.** To maintain the relevance and focus of our study, we excluded literature that did not align with the primary objectives of wetland restoration or lacked substantial information regarding success factors.

We conducted the SCOPUS literature search on December 5, 2023, utilising the search string "wetland restoration" OR "floodplain restoration." The search parameters included article titles, abstracts, and keywords.

The review process involved a thorough title and abstract screening, full-text review, and data extraction to filter out articles that did not meet the inclusion criteria. During the full-text review, we extracted relevant data, focusing on wetland restoration success factors and contextual information.

2.2 THEMATIC ANALYSIS

A thematic analysis was then applied to the findings of the literature review via systematic coding. The analysis aimed at pinpointing the dominant views of wetland restoration projects by identifying recurring patterns, themes, and success factors across the selected literature. Thematic coding facilitated the organisation and analysis of the identified information, ensuring a more nuanced understanding of wetland restoration success factors. The thematic analysis was developed deductively employing the available theory on successful ecological restoration. The frequency of a theme's occurrence within the texts did not necessarily reflect its importance but rather highlighted distinct patterns.

Expert opinion was sought to complement the findings from the literature review and thematic analysis. Project partners contributed their knowledge and expertise, enriching the understanding and classification of wetland restoration success factors. This systematic approach ensured a thorough exploration of relevant literature and a nuanced understanding of the subject matter.

2.3 QUESTIONNAIRE DEVELOPMENT

The previous findings informed the development of a questionnaire designed using Google Forms. The questionnaire was distributed online to all project partners to collect initial information that will further populate the Restore4Life Wetland Restoration online database. The questionnaire contained questions providing factual data on wetland restoration projects in the Danube Basin/ Europe, linking various themes that were derived from literature review with the main project phases: i) pre-restoration phase, ii) implementation phase, and iii) post-restoration or monitoring phase.

3 WETLAND RESTORATION SUCCESS FACTORS

A wetland restoration project may be considered successful from multiple perspectives. In this chapter, we elaborate on our evaluation by interpreting success through the following perspectives: ecological, societal, and community engagement, governance and policy, functional, climate adaptation, adaptive management and monitoring, financial and business support, and communication and outreach.

3.1 PERSPECTIVES OF WETLAND RESTORATION SUCCESS

The literature search returned 94 results, and the detailed list is provided in Appendix A.

The thematic analysis of selected review papers complemented by project partners' expert opinion (scientists and practitioners alike) revealed multiple perspectives on wetland restoration success. Under each perspective, several success factors were identified at various levels of granularity. Each success factor was further defined by an indefinite number of indicators to offer tangible and quantifiable evidence of the restoration's success. It is important to note that several success factors may fall into more than one perspective; for example, collecting stakeholder feedback on the management process (success factor) via satisfaction surveys (success indicator) and integration of this feedback into management plans (success indicator) may be analysed from different perspectives: societal and community engagement, governance and policy, and adaptive management and monitoring perspectives.

The results of the thematic analysis endeavour are presented in Table 1, where each success perspective nests several success factors, with each factor nesting several indicators. It is important to note that our selection of factors and indicators in Table 1 is not exclusive and just presents an example.

TABLE 1. WETLAND RESTORATION SUCCESS PERSPECTIVES DERIVED FROM LITERATURE

Examples of success factors	Examples of success indicators	Possible assessment questions
Ecological and functional perspective		
Baseline assessment of biotic and abiotic components	Comprehensive assessment of the pre-restoration state of the wetland ecosystem Site suitability analysis	Completed ecological surveys; Documentation of baseline data on biodiversity and ES Assessments of hydrology, soil, vegetation etc.
		What comprehensive technical assessments were conducted before restoration? Please briefly describe baseline information on biodiversity and ecosystem services pre-restoration.

Ecosystem services provision	Increase of ecosystem services array Continued provision of ES	Ratio between ES provided pre- and post- restoration Monitoring of water purification services; Assessment of recreational opportunities post-restoration	Have there been noticeable increases in the types and provision of ecosystem services post-restoration?
Ecosystem resilience to climate stressors	Monitoring and demonstrating the ecosystem's resilience to climate-induced stressors	Documentation of ecosystem recovery following extreme climate events (floods, draughts, other); Presence/ number of climate-resilient and adaptive species.	How has the ecosystem demonstrated resilience to climate-induced stressors post-restoration? Can you provide examples of ecosystem recovery following extreme climate events?

Societal and community engagement perspective

Community involvement and participation	Active involvement of local communities in wetland restoration decision-making	Percentage of community members participating in planning meetings/ restoration related activities Number of community-led initiatives within the restoration area	Were local communities involved in decision-making during the restoration process? Please describe how local communities were engaged.
Local knowledge integration	Incorporation of local and traditional knowledge and/or methods into the wetland restoration process Use of local and traditional knowledge within the restored wetland area	Documentation of TEK applied in the restoration project Documentation of TEK used within/ in relation to the restored area Number of traditional practices integrated into the project Number / Percentage of local population engaged in traditional practices in relation to the restored area	Was local and traditional ecological knowledge incorporated into the restoration process? Please describe. Are there any traditional practices currently used within the restored area? (e.g. fishing, reed harvesting, ecotourism)
Education and capacity building	Building community capacity through educational programs on wetland ecosystems and restoration practices	Number of workshops or training sessions conducted Increase in knowledge levels within the community	Were any educational programs implemented to build community capacity before, during or post-restoration project? Please describe.
Long-term community commitment, stewardship and citizen science	Fostering a sense of long-term commitment and stewardship toward the restored wetland post-restoration	Creation and sustainability of local wetland management committees Continued community involvement in post-restoration monitoring	Are there any local committees/ working groups/ mini-public assemblies constituted in relation to the restored wetland area management/ governance? Please describe. Are there any citizen science initiatives dealing with post-restoration monitoring in the restored area and/or adjacent ecosystems? Please describe.

Governance and policy perspective

Policy alignment and integration	Alignment of wetland restoration projects with existing national and regional policies	Integration of wetland restoration goals in policy documents Documentation of policy alignment assessments	How were wetland restoration goals integrated into existing policies? Can you provide examples of policy alignment assessments?
Clear regulatory frameworks	Establishment of clear regulatory frameworks governing wetland restoration activities	Presence of well-defined regulations for wetland restoration	What regulatory frameworks govern wetland restoration activities in your project?
Property rights systems	Clear delineation of property rights	Clear delineation of property rights, including ownership, access rights, and land use regulations	What property rights system governs the wetland restoration area? Are there clear delineations of property rights, including ownership, access rights, and land use regulations? How do property rights systems facilitate or hinder wetland restoration efforts? Have conflicts over property rights arisen during the restoration process, and if so, how were they addressed?
Multi-stakeholder collaboration	Collaboration between various stakeholders, including government agencies, research, NGOs, and local communities during the planning phase	Number of stakeholders / stakeholder types involved in the planning process Frequency of collaborative meetings and workshops	Can you provide examples of successful collaboration or conflict resolution related to property rights within the restoration area? Describe the collaboration between various stakeholders during the planning phase. What types of actors were involved (e.g. national and or/local decision-makers, researchers, local community representatives, youth etc) in the planning process?
Community consultations & participation in decision-making processes	Inclusion of local communities in decision-making processes related to wetland restoration	Number of community consultations conducted during the planning phase Degree of incorporation of community inputs into restoration plans	How frequently were collaborative meetings/consultations/workshops held? To what degree were civil society/ community inputs incorporated into restoration plans?

Adaptive management and monitoring perspective

Integration of adaptive management strategies based on ongoing monitoring feedback	Integration of adaptive management strategies based on ongoing monitoring feedback	Number of implemented adaptive management interventions Adjustments made to restoration plans based on monitoring results	Can you provide examples of adaptive management interventions implemented based on monitoring feedback? How often were restoration plans adjusted based on monitoring results?
Post-restoration monitoring continuity	Post-restoration monitoring continuity	Existence of post-restoration monitoring protocols Community involvement in continued monitoring efforts	Are there established post-restoration monitoring protocols? How is the community involved in continued monitoring efforts?
Adaptive strategies for future challenges	Development of adaptive strategies for potential future challenges	Identification of future climate change scenarios and associated risks Integration of adaptive strategies into long-term management plans	Have climate change scenarios been identified for the restored wetland area? Have adaptive strategies been integrated into long-term management plans? How frequently are knowledge-sharing sessions conducted to review monitoring results and further facilitate continuous learning and adaptation?
Learning and knowledge sharing	Regular review and sharing of monitoring results for continuous learning and adaptation	Frequency of knowledge-sharing sessions Documentation of lessons learned and best practices	Is there documentation of lessons learned and best practices from the restoration project to inform future initiatives and decision-making processes? Have satisfaction surveys been conducted to gather feedback on the monitoring and adaptive management processes?
Integration of stakeholder feedback	Collection of stakeholder feedback on the monitoring and adaptive management processes	Satisfaction surveys Integration of stakeholder feedback in future planning	How is stakeholder feedback integrated into future planning processes to ensure alignment with stakeholders' needs and expectations?

Communication and outreach perspective

Public Awareness and Advocacy	Public awareness and advocacy initiatives supporting wetland conservation and restoration	Reach and engagement on advocacy campaigns post-restoration Public perceptions and attitudes toward the restored wetland	What initiatives were undertaken to raise public awareness about wetland conservation and restoration? How successful have these initiatives been in engaging the public?
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Financial and business support perspective

Strategic financial planning	Development of a comprehensive financial plan aligned with restoration goals	The existence of a detailed budget for the entire project Identification of potential funding sources	How was the project's financial plan developed and aligned with restoration goals? Can you provide details about potential funding sources identified?
Business sector engagement	Involvement and support from businesses in the planning phase Continued support and engagement from businesses after the restoration phase Ongoing collaboration with businesses for sustained support Engagement with businesses through Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) or ESG programs Successful submission of grant applications and securing initial funding	Number of established business partnerships; Commitment levels from business stakeholders Business commitment to long-term restoration goals Number of active business enterprises post-restoration; No of business initiatives and projects in/ close to/ related to the restored area Number of CSR partnerships/ initiatives; Measurable impacts of CSR initiatives on restoration	Describe the involvement and support from businesses in the planning phase, during and/or post-restoration. Have there been any measurable impacts of CSR initiatives on restoration?
Funding and grant applications	Utilisation of various funding streams for ongoing support Establishment of sustainable funding mechanisms for post-restoration activities	Amount of initial funding secured Number of funding sources (European, government, private, crowdsourcing...); Percentage of the budget covered by diverse funding Continuity of funding post-restoration; Development of a sustainable funding mechanism	How successful were grant applications in securing initial funding? What mechanisms are in place to ensure sustainable funding post-restoration?
Economic assessment	Assessment of the economic impact of the restoration project (e.g. Civitta study for Mahmudia)	Evaluation of the project's contribution to the local economy Measurement of economic benefits	What methods were used to assess the economic impact of the restoration project? Can you share any findings regarding the project's contribution to the local economy?

Climate adaptation perspective

Incorporation of climate projections	Utilization of climate change projections to inform long-term management and restoration strategies	Presence of climate change projections incorporated into long-term management plans	Are climate change projections utilized to inform the long-term management of the restored wetland?
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Integration of Climate Resilience Strategies	Implementation of adaptive strategies to enhance the wetland ecosystem's resilience to climate change impacts	Number of climate adaptation strategies integrated into restoration plans and/or management plans of restored areas	Were any specific climate resilience strategies implemented during the wetland restoration project?
Flexibility in management plans	Adjusting management plans in response to changing climate conditions and associated risks	Presence of adjustments made to management plans based on observed/projected climate impacts	Were there any adjustments or modifications made to the management plans in response to observed climate impacts during the project?

By expanding on each of the perspectives mentioned in Table 1, we provide a comprehensive understanding of the multiple dimensions that contribute to the success of wetland restoration projects. Each perspective includes specific factors and indicators, along with examples, to illustrate how these aspects are measured and achieved in real-world projects.

3.1.1 ECOLOGICAL AND FUNCTIONAL PERSPECTIVE

Factors contributing to success included achieving specific functional goals of the restoration endeavour, such as improved water quality, enhanced flood control, increased biodiversity of target organisms, and the improvement of overall ecological functions. Additionally, the increase in the number and provision of ecosystem services, inherently linked to ecological functions, was identified as a key indicator of success. This includes fostering win-win situations (e.g. floodwater and nutrient retention) and alleviating potential trade-offs (e.g. biodiversity vs. food provisioning). For example, restoration plans in a floodplain of the Austrian Danube highlighted win-win situations dominating among regulating ES (dynamic habitats, nutrient retention) but local trade-offs between regulating and cultural ES (e.g. hiking and cycling) due to restricted accessibility (Funk et al. 2021). Identifying trade-offs and, in turn, offering compensations (alternative hiking and cycling paths) to the affected stakeholders can substantially increase restoration success.

Restoration success indicators act on different spatial and temporal scales (Tschikof et al. 2024) and must be assessed accordingly. Whereas large-scale functions, such as climate regulation, respond slowly to restoration measures and are usually modelled regionally, functions acting on smaller scale must be investigated locally, such as e.g. the immediate colonialization of suitable habitats for protected fish. Therefore, the evaluation of restoration success should also consider the ecosystem functions and services over the edge of the wetland and beyond the immediate effects of a measure.

3.1.2 SOCIETAL AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT PERSPECTIVE

Success in this perspective is linked to community engagement, stakeholder involvement, and consideration of local needs and values. Positive impacts on local communities' livelihoods and well-being were identified as indicators of successful wetland restoration projects. Citizen Science, i.e. the active involvement of the local community in data collection and monitoring, has proven to be an effective tool to raise the awareness of the sensitivity and value of intact wetlands and thus to enhance the support of restoration measures by the

local community. Involving Citizen Scientists in the data collection of the success monitoring can significantly increase data availability and spatial and temporal data resolution which may otherwise not be feasible if properly designed, carried out, and evaluated. Furthermore, including local knowledge already in the planning and implementation of restoration activities are key to increasing stewardship of citizens and securing the successful long-term restoration and protection of wetlands. The local community can identify problems or issues not apparent to outsiders, thus helping government agencies and other organizations in formulating and implementing public policy, assessing potential societal and ecological impacts of decisions, and even enforcing regulations pertaining to conservation, natural resources, and the environment (McKinley et al 2017).

3.1.3 GOVERNANCE AND POLICY PERSPECTIVE

Governance and policy are pivotal in the success of wetland restoration projects and play a crucial role in sustainable development and natural resource management. Effective governance ensures restoration efforts are empirically grounded, inclusive, participatory, and well-funded. Governance frameworks dictate decision-making processes, power dynamics, and stakeholder participation, significantly conditioning the effectiveness of conservation efforts and their contribution to human well-being (Springer et al., 2021).

Successful natural resource management is a complex task that extends beyond ecological restoration techniques. It involves creating a cooperative environment involving various stakeholders. Socio-economic and governmental systems, rather than environmental factors, are often the primary obstacles to successful restoration in Europe. Conflicting stakeholder interests, lack of funding, and low political priority for wetland issues are major hindrances (Cortina-Segarra et al., 2021).

Global frameworks such as the Ramsar Convention and the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) provide essential guidelines for sustainable wetland management. The Ramsar Convention emphasizes the "wise use" of wetlands through sustainable development and international cooperation. At the same time, the GBF sets ambitious restoration targets and highlights the importance of disaster risk reduction and financial resource mobilization.

European directives like the Water Framework Directive (WFD) and the Floods Directive (FD) promote integrated planning and sustainable land use, providing substantial opportunities for wetland restoration. The European Green Deal and the proposed Nature Restoration Law further support these efforts by setting ambitious targets for ecosystem restoration and biodiversity conservation.

Regional frameworks such as the Danube River Protection Convention (DRPC) demonstrate the importance of transboundary cooperation in wetland management. The DRPC's collaborative approach, involving both EU and non-EU countries, underscores the need to align upstream and downstream interests for sustainable water resource management.

Incorporating governance and policy perspectives in wetland restoration projects is crucial for long-term success. Overcoming weak and fragmented governance systems and

enhancing participation and democracy are essential. Better policies and integration of best practices from past restoration projects are needed to identify innovative pathways that support large-scale wetland restoration. Aligning scientific, social, and economic objectives through robust governance frameworks ensures the sustainability and effectiveness of these initiatives. The IUCN defines Natural Resource Governance as the norms, institutions and processes that determine how power and responsibilities over natural resources are exercised, how decisions are taken, and how citizens — including women, men, youth, indigenous peoples and local communities — participate in and benefit from the management of natural resources" (Springer et al., 2021).

3.1.4 ADAPTIVE MANAGEMENT AND MONITORING PERSPECTIVE

The ability to adjust restoration approaches based on ongoing assessment and continuous learning contributes to long-term success. Adaptive management strategies enhance the resilience of restoration projects to changing environmental conditions. Adaptive management is a learning process about the system and its restoration responses that requires setting goals and a monitoring component that lasts sufficiently long (Patten 2006). Scientific monitoring activities of the wetland's state inform managers on alternative decisions necessary to increase restoration success. Ultimately, the trajectories of change must be understood which guide decisions on whether and how to continue restoration activities. Adaptive management includes developing a catalogue of flexible measures which allow to incorporate new findings from the monitoring into the integrative planning and implementation process.

3.1.5 COMMUNICATION AND OUTREACH PERSPECTIVE

Wetland restoration projects face challenges due to negative public perceptions and limited awareness of the benefits wetlands provide to society. Effective communication of these benefits has been insufficient; to address this, an ecosystem service approach has been recommended, highlighting the connection between wetland functions and human well-being to improve public understanding (Scholte et al., 2016).

Effective communication and public engagement are crucial in ecological restoration projects. Restoration managers need to engage with community members and stakeholders throughout the process, using iterative communication to co-create knowledge and build trust. This communication allows for stakeholder satisfaction, advances in scientific knowledge and management practices, and ecological improvements. Managers should consider their desired social-ecological outcomes and design mechanisms for sustained and consequential communication and public engagement involving community stakeholders in all phases of restoration projects (Druschke and Hychka, 2015).

Employing a communication and outreach perspective in wetland restoration projects enhances stakeholder involvement, builds trust and credibility among actors, educates and raises awareness, fosters collaboration and partnerships, and supports adaptive

management. These elements are essential for achieving successful and sustainable restoration outcomes.

3.1.6 FINANCIAL AND BUSINESS SUPPORT PERSPECTIVE

Water resources today are invariably owned and managed by the state. To the extent that private sector businesses have a direct involvement it is chiefly based on implementing and/or benefiting from government policies, regulations, and schemes. These range from the macro (e.g. potable water supply and wastewater treatment, hydroelectric power generation, land drainage and flood protection, crop irrigation, and navigation) to the micro (e.g. angling licences, car washes, wells and water-based recreation) economic levels. Governments now oversee vast infrastructure networks developed over centuries that are increasingly under stress from unsustainable use practices and climate change impacts. There is growing recognition that the existing water supply models are failing and there is a need to design new approaches to water use that incorporate nature-based solutions as well as economic tools such as realistic water pricing, punitive fines for abuses and adoption of more efficient water-saving technologies.

In terms of nature-based solutions, the aim is to restore as far as possible functioning aquatic ecosystem services for the long term, as set out elsewhere in this report. Success in this respect will depend on new well-informed government policies, the availability of funding sources, the alignment of financial incentives with conservation goals, and the ability to attract investment from businesses and philanthropic organisations. This combination of ecological and economic tools must also serve societal interests over the long (intergenerational) term – the fundamental basis of sustainable development.

Measures with a focus on developing a dynamic pro-nature business sector should include targeting of rural development and loan guarantee funds to nature-based business sectors such as:

- Forestry (planting of native species);
- Environmentally friendly agriculture;
- Organic fisheries;
- Green tourism; and
- Biomass energy (green carbon).

3.1.7 CLIMATE ADAPTATION PERSPECTIVE

Understanding the significant challenges that climate change poses to the long-term viability and effectiveness of natural or restored wetlands (Erwin 2008) is crucial. By incorporating a climate adaptation perspective, we can design and implement wetland restoration projects that consider the potential impacts of climate change. This approach ensures the resilience and adaptability of the restored wetland ecosystem (Colloff et al. 2016). Conversely, wetland restoration is a key player in climate change mitigation through various mechanisms (Bertolini

and da Mosto, 2021). It aids in carbon dioxide sequestration and storage, methane emission reduction, coastal protection, water quality improvement, and biodiversity conservation. Wetlands act as natural carbon sinks, capturing and storing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere. They also help reduce methane emissions by acting as sinks for methane. Additionally, wetlands act as natural buffers against coastal erosion and storm surges, improve water quality by filtering and purifying water, and provide habitat for a wide range of species. By restoring and conserving wetlands, their capacity to mitigate climate change is enhanced.

The climate adaptation perspective can be incorporated into wetland restoration projects in several ways:

- Assessing climate change impacts. Before initiating a wetland restoration project, it is vital to assess the potential impacts of climate change on the target ecosystem (Colloff et al., 2016). This involves studying climate projections, hydrological changes, and other relevant factors to understand how the wetland may be affected.
- Designing for resilience. Wetland restoration projects should be designed to enhance the resilience of the ecosystem to climate change. This can include selecting native plant species that are more tolerant to changing climatic conditions, creating diverse habitats to support a range of species, and incorporating natural buffers to protect against extreme weather events.
- Incorporating adaptive management. Wetland restoration projects should be implemented with an adaptive management approach, which involves monitoring the ecosystem's response to restoration efforts and adjusting as needed. This allows for ongoing assessment and adaptation to changing conditions, ensuring that the restored wetland remains effective in the face of climate change.
- Considering future scenarios. Wetland restoration projects should consider future climate scenarios and incorporate flexibility to accommodate potential changes. This can involve designing restoration strategies adaptable to different climate conditions and considering the potential need for future adjustments or modifications.
- Incorporating a climate adaptation perspective in wetland restoration projects is a collaborative effort that requires the engagement of stakeholders. These include local communities, scientists, policymakers, and other relevant parties. Their involvement in the planning and decision-making process is crucial to ensuring that the project addresses their needs and concerns in the context of climate change.

3.2 RESTORATION PROJECTS QUESTIONNAIRE RESULTS

Based on the perspectives identified in previous steps, a questionnaire was designed and sent to project partners to collect initial data on European wetland restoration projects. Partners' input will further populate the Wetland Restoration Wiki, facilitating knowledge exchange and guiding future restoration efforts.

COUNTRIES RESPONDING TO THE QUESTIONNAIRE

Figure 2. Map and percentage of the countries responding to the questionnaire about the wetland restoration success factors in Europe

Out of eleven countries that provided data in response to the questionnaire on wetland restoration success factors in Europe, nine are located within the Danube Basin. Although the Danube Basin encompasses 19 countries (ICPDR DRMP, 2021), the responding countries covered a combined area of 711,729 km² out of a total 803,260 km². Additionally, the Netherlands and Spain also contributed data on restoration success factors.

Notably, Bulgaria exceeded expectations by submitting 26 wetland restoration cases. Other countries with significant contributions include Croatia, Romania, and Hungary. The German site was particularly well-documented, providing comprehensive information, including geographical data (shapefiles, pictures, etc.).

GEOGRAPHICAL COORDINATES

Geographical coordinates were provided for fifty-eight restoration sites. Figure 2 illustrates a map of these restoration sites as of May 2024. The number of the restoration sites is expected to increase, enhancing future data analysis.

Figure 3. Map of the restored sites based on the questionnaire for wetland restoration success (as of May 2024). The current sites include: 1 Lower March floodplains; 2 Lower Traisen; 3 Persina Nature Park and Kalimok/Brushlen; 4 Persina Nature Park and Kalimok/Brushlen; 5 Lake Varna; 6 Atanasovsko Lake; 7 Ropotamo, Poda, Vaya; 8 NA; 9 Kaykusha marsh; 10 Foros bay; 11 Persina; 12 Kalimok Wetlands; 13 Lake Durankulak/Lake Shabla; 14 Lake Burgas; 15 Kalimok – Brashlen; 16 Srebarna Lake; 17 Mesta/Nestos River; 18 Aaos/Vjosa River; 19 Vardar/Axios River; 20 Region Of Thessaly; 21 Lake Pomorie – Bulgaria Danube Biosphere Reserve; 22 Pomorie Lake; 23 Dragoman Marsh; 24 Otok Virje; 25 Stara Drava Varaždin; 26 Donja Dubrava – Legrad; 27 Most Botovo; 28 Novačka; 29 Miholjački Martinci; 30 Podravska Moslavina; 31 Neuburg and Ingolstadt; 32 Bática; 33 Püspökszilágy; 34 Rákócziújfalu; 35 Ruzsa; 36 Tiszatarján; 37 Perkpolder; 38 Small Island of Braila Natural Park; 39 Zaghen; 40 Mătăsaru–Fusea; 41 Balta Geraiului; 42 Carasuhat; 43 Gârla Mare – Vrata; 44 Babina Cernovca; 45 Gornje Podunavlje; 46 Gornje Podunavlje; 47 Milica Stojković Piperac; 48 Dunajské luhy; 49 Doňana

PROJECT NAME AND REFERENCE

Out of the 53 sites surveyed, 37 provided project names and references. This information will facilitate better data verification and ensure the accurate tracking of restoration projects in Europe, with a particular focus on the Danube Delta Basin. Among the projects that provided names, 11 were financed through the EU-LIFE mechanism.

TIMING OF RESTORATION PROJECTS

According to the data provided through the questionnaire, most restoration sites have an average restoration age of about 5 years. Only two projects out of the 46 analysed are older than 14 years.

Figure 4. a. Average time of the restoration projects; b. The difference between the planning phase and the implementation phase (average 5.4 years, with a minimum of 1 and a maximum of 11 years for planning; 4 years on average, with a maximum of 7 years for implementation)

The duration of both the planning and implementation phases is crucial in determining the average time required to complete these complex projects. Wetland restoration projects are particularly complex and challenging. Collected data showed that on average, the planning phase lasted about 5.4 years (n=11), while the implementation phase took approximately 4 years (n=16).

SURFACE OF THE RESTORED AREA

Out of the 53 sites surveyed, only 25 reported surface data. The total restored area over the years exceeds 100,000 hectares, which is relatively small compared to the necessity and targets set in various policy papers, such as the goal of restoring 27,100 km². To better represent changes in the wetland restoration rate, we plotted the sum of the area of restored wetlands over 5-year periods from 1996 to 2023 (Figure 4).

Figure 5. Total restored wetland area for questionnaire sites over the period 1996–2023 (27 years)

As shown in the graph, the wetland restoration rate has increased over the years. However, based on this preliminary data, the current restoration rate is much lower than needed. With an average restoration rate ranging between 66 to 2,700 hectares per year, it is unlikely that the target of 2.7 million hectares will be met in the near or even long-term future.

Achieving such ambitious targets requires a paradigm shift, including a greater understanding and appreciation of the value of wetlands. Wetlands are incredibly valuable ecosystems that provide numerous ecosystem services to humans, and recognizing this importance is crucial for driving more effective restoration efforts.

DESIGNATION AND PROTECTION STATUS

Figure 6. Designation and protection status of the wetland restoration sites

Most of the responses included restoration sites that are designated as Natura 2000 sites, with a quarter being designated Ramsar sites, and a few biosphere reserves.

ECOLOGICAL AND FUNCTIONAL PERSPECTIVE

From the ecological and functional perspective of restoration success, a total of 9 indicators have been proposed: 1) main objectives of the wetland restoration; 2) indicators used before and after restoration (species composition); 3) structural diversity; 4) physical conditions; 5) ecosystem functioning; 6) species traits; 7) Landscape type (before/after); 8) restoration measures or techniques used and finally 9) enhanced types of ES after restoration

Out of these dimensions, we have chosen to present 6, while the remaining questions have generated descriptive responses.

MAIN OBJECTIVES OF THE RESTORATION

Figure 7. Main restoration objectives in wetland restoration

The results indicate that the most frequent objectives of wetland restoration projects assessed here were habitat and/or ecosystem recovery and species restoration.

INDICATORS USED BEFORE(PLANNING) AND POST(MONITORING) RESTORATION - SPECIES COMPOSITION

Species composition is a good indicator for understanding and managing wetland ecosystems. It provides essential information about the diversity, health, and ecological balance of the community, guiding conservation and restoration efforts.

Figure 8. Species composition indicator

In many of the cases the species composition (species abundance, occurrence and specific target species) is being used in both phases but this is more the case in the monitoring phase.

INDICATORS USED BEFORE (PLANNING) AND POST (MONITORING) RESTORATION - STRUCTURAL DIVERSITY

Structural diversity in wetlands refers to the variety of physical forms and spatial arrangements of both biotic (living) and abiotic (non-living) components within the ecosystem. This diversity is a crucial aspect of wetland health and functionality, influencing numerous ecological processes and supporting a wide range of species. We used a definition that is taking into consideration density/ abundance of species; functional composition; habitat distribution and vegetation. In a wetland ecosystem, functional composition might include traits related to water tolerance, root structure, and reproductive strategies. Plants with different root structures (e.g., deep roots vs. shallow roots) contribute differently to soil stabilization and water filtration. By analysing the functional composition, ecologists can predict how changes in species composition might affect the overall functioning of the wetland.

Figure 9. Structural diversity indicator

The structural diversity in wetland restoration has been used both in the planning phase and in the monitoring phase of the restoration projects.

INDICATORS USED BEFORE (PLANNING) AND POST (MONITORING) RESTORATION - PHYSICAL CONDITIONS

Physical indicators are essential tools for understanding, managing, and restoring wetland ecosystems. They encompass a broad range of parameters, including water characteristics, soil properties, and microclimatic conditions.

Figure 10. Structural physical conditions

For the indicators related to the physical conditions there is a clear difference between the planning phase and the monitoring phase.

INDICATORS USED BEFORE(PLANNING) AND POST (MONITORING) RESTORATION - ECOSYSTEM FUNCTIONING

Ecosystem functioning refers to the biological, geochemical, and physical processes and components that take place or exist within an ecosystem. It is a critical indicator of ecosystem health, resilience, and productivity, encompassing various processes such as nutrient cycling, primary production, decomposition, and energy flow.

Figure 11. Ecosystem functioning

Like for the physical conditions the ecosystem functioning is treated with more attention in the second phase after the project (in the monitoring phase). Monitoring the ecosystem functioning is a difficult process that requires careful attention and adequate planning but could potentially provide much more indications about the restoration projects.

WHICH TYPE(S) OF ECOSYSTEM SERVICES DISPLAYED NOTICEABLE INCREASES POST-RESTORATION?

Wetlands provide a wide array of ecosystem services that benefit human populations. Restoration efforts aim to reestablish the natural functions and processes of degraded or lost wetlands, leading to enhanced provision of these services and therefore the questionnaire addressed also this dimension.

Figure 12. Ecosystem services' changes observed after project implementation

Many respondents have stressed the importance of restoration especially for regulating and supporting ES, but it is to be noticed that all classes of ES are increasing after restoration activities.

SOCIETAL AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT PERSPECTIVE

In addition to the ecological perspective, we also examined the societal and community engagement aspect. This perspective encompasses various considerations, including the involvement of different stakeholders in the restoration process, such as civil society and businesses. We evaluated the impact of restoration efforts on local communities, taking into account factors like the existence and timing of consultation processes. Additionally, we assessed whether traditional knowledge was integrated into the restoration initiatives. Recognizing the importance of capacity building, we emphasized the need for enhancing local capabilities and ensuring social acceptance of the restoration processes.

How were civil society/ local communities/ businesses and other affected stakeholders engaged in decision-making during the restoration process?

Many different methods of engagement have been used in different restoration sites to allow the local communities to participate in the co-creation and co-development process of wetland restoration.

Figure 13. Engagement methods used in wetland restoration sites

The results presented shows in fact the need for a coherent approach towards a more focused process long before any restoration process. The need of a stepwise process starting with education and outreach programs, community meeting and participatory mapping is highlighted.

In what phases of the restoration process were civil society/ local communities/ businesses and other affected stakeholder engaged?

Engaging stakeholders is very important, but equally important is when are the stakeholders involved. Timing is very important, and it is obvious that all the phases are equally important from planning to implementation and post-restoration in order to ensure the sustainability of the restored area.

Figure 14. Involving stakeholders in different phases of the restoration process

GOVERNANCE AND POLICY PERSPECTIVE

Here the governance and policy perspective has been assessed. Different dimensions have been considered from the property rights system that governs the restoration area to the

obstacles that arose during any of the restoration process phases including unclear legal framework, legal framework had to be updated, insufficient technical capacity, insufficient local community not in favour, interest group strong lobby, obtaining licenses etc.

ADAPTIVE MANAGEMENT AND MONITORING PERSPECTIVE

THE USE OF CLIMATE CHANGE PROJECTIONS

Many of the above questions could be also included in this perspective dealing with adaptative management and monitoring. We have considered that the climate change is something that should be taken into consideration when dealing with wetland restoration due to the nature of ecosystems being restored.

Figure 15. Climate change projections included in wetland restoration planning

In many cases (from a total of 39 responses) the wetland restoration is not considering the climate change in the planning phase. This could have important long-term consequences on the sustainability of the results of such projects especially due to the sensitivity of the wetland to hydrological regimen.

COMMUNICATION AND OUTREACH PERSPECTIVE

Here we have address different ways to raise awareness about the need of wetland restoration by investigating what types of initiatives were undertaken to raise awareness about wetland restoration.

In many cases the initiatives were quite diverse from website, social media platforms, events and meetings, mass media (local, national and international), public reports, educational programs for wetlands management etc.

FINANCIAL AND BUSINESS SUPPORT PERSPECTIVE

Finally we have assessed the financial and business perspective. In many cases the financial support was provided by international funding organizations (26%) of the cases and governmental grants and funding.

Figure 16. Type of financial support for wetland restoration

4 CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

The results of our study reveal that the evaluation of a restoration project extends beyond ecological metrics alone and ideally takes place within and between its three major phases: planning, implementation and post-implementation. Findings also show multifaceted perspectives on wetland restoration success, encompassing a broad spectrum of elements shaping positive outcomes. From ecological considerations to governance structures, socioeconomic impacts, and climate change adaptation, these factors collectively shape wetland restoration projects. These findings underscore the complex nature of wetland restoration endeavours and the importance of considering diverse factors in evaluating success.

Our findings, which align with previous research, highlight the interdependence of ecological health, societal well-being, and effective governance in wetland restoration efforts. The identification of success factors across various dimensions contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of restoration outcomes. This understanding can guide future research and practice, leading to more effective and sustainable wetland restoration efforts.

Practical implications of our findings for practitioners, policymakers, and stakeholders are important. By recognizing the significance of ecological functionality, community engagement, supportive governance structures, adaptive management strategies, effective communication, and financial sustainability, restoration initiatives can be more effectively planned, implemented, and evaluated. Our contribution to the wetland restoration literature lies in providing a nuanced exploration of success factors from inter- and transdisciplinary perspectives. The development of the Wetland Restoration Wiki serves as a vital resource for knowledge exchange and experience sharing among stakeholders, facilitating informed decision-making and enhancing the effectiveness of restoration efforts.

Reflecting on key success factors emphasizes the interconnectedness of various elements and the collective impact of restoration projects. The dynamic nature of wetland restoration requires adaptive strategies that respond to a changing world, underscoring the need for flexible and iterative approaches to restoration efforts.

A holistic approach to sustainable development recognizes that success extends beyond ecological metrics alone, necessitating consideration of community well-being, adherence to legal frameworks, and involvement of diverse stakeholders. Understanding the intricate relationships between these factors is essential for achieving long-term success.

Emphasizing collaboration and knowledge exchange as crucial, collective wisdom—spanning scientists, policymakers, practitioners, local businesses, and communities—is needed to advance wetland restoration science and practice.

Moving forward, the catalogue and wiki provide a foundation for informed decision-making, serving as sources of inspiration for future initiatives. The identified success factors offer a roadmap for guiding restoration efforts, ensuring the continued preservation and enhancement of wetland ecosystems.

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APPENDIX A SCOPUS LITERATURE SURVEY RESULTS

No. crt	Authors	Title	Year	Source title
1	Acreman M.; Smith A.; Charters L.; Tickner D.; Opperman J.; Acreman S.; Edwards F.; Sayers P.; Chivava F.	Evidence for the effectiveness of nature-based solutions to water issues in Africa	2021	Environmental Research Letters
2	Acreman M.C.; Harding R.J.; Lloyd C.; McNamara N.P.; Mountford J.O.; Mould D.J.; Purse B.V.; Heard M.S.; Stratford C.J.; Dury S.J.	Trade-off in ecosystem services of the Somerset Levels and Moors wetlands	2011	Hydrological Sciences Journal
3	Adame M.F.; Arthington A.H.; Waltham N.; Hasan S.; Selles A.; Ronan M.	Managing threats and restoring wetlands within catchments of the Great Barrier Reef, Australia	2019	Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems
4	Adams C.R.; Hovick S.M.; Anderson N.O.; Kettnering K.M.	We Can Better Manage Ecosystems by Connecting Solutions to Constraints: Learning from Wetland Plant Invasions	2021	Frontiers in Environmental Science
5	An S.; Tian Z.; Cai Y.; Wen T.; Xu D.; Jiang H.; Yao Z.; Guan B.; Sheng S.; Ouyang Y.; Cheng X.	Wetlands of Northeast Asia and High Asia: An overview	2013	Aquatic Sciences
6	Angeler D.G.; Chow-Fraser P.; Hanson M.A.; Sánchez-Carrillo S.; Zimmer K.D.	Bio-manipulation: A useful tool for freshwater wetland mitigation?	2003	Freshwater Biology
7	Banerjee S.; Secchi S.; Fargione J.; Polasky S.; Kraft S.	How to sell ecosystem services: A guide for designing new markets	2013	Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment
8	Bauer D.M.; Cyr N.E.; Swallow S.K.	Public preferences for compensatory mitigation of salt marsh losses: A contingent choice of alternatives	2004	Conservation Biology
9	Bertolini C.; da Mosto J.	Restoring for the climate: a review of coastal wetland restoration research in the last 30 years	2021	Restoration Ecology
10	Birchell G.J.; Christopherson K.D.	Growth and survival of larval razorback sucker in natural floodplain depressions inhabited by nonnative fish in the Green River, Utah	2005	American Fisheries Society Symposium
11	Birnbaum C.; Trevathan-Tackett S.M.	Aiding coastal wetland restoration via the belowground soil microbiome: an overview	2023	Restoration Ecology
12	Bring A.; Rosén L.; Thorslund J.; Tonderski K.; Åberg C.; Envall I.; Laudon H.	Groundwater storage effects from restoring, constructing or draining wetlands in temperate and boreal climates: a systematic review protocol	2020	Environmental Evidence

No. crt	Authors	Title	Year	Source title
13	Bring A.; Thorslund J.; Rosén L.; Tonderski K.; Åberg C.; Envall I.; Laudon H.	Effects on groundwater storage of restoring, constructing or draining wetlands in temperate and boreal climates: a systematic review	2022	Environmental Evidence
14	Browne M.; Fraser G.; Snowball J.	Economic evaluation of wetland restoration: a systematic review of the literature	2018	Restoration Ecology
15	Cadier C.; Bayraktarov E.; Piccolo R.; Adame M.F.	Indicators of Coastal Wetlands Restoration Success: A Systematic Review	2020	Frontiers in Marine Science
16	Cai Y.; Liang J.; Zhang P.; Wang Q.; Wu Y.; Ding Y.; Wang H.; Fu C.; Sun J.	Review on strategies of close-to-natural wetland restoration and a brief case plan for a typical wetland in northern China	2021	Chemosphere
17	Callaway J.C.	The challenge of restoring functioning salt marsh ecosystems	2005	Journal of Coastal Research
18	Canning A.D.; Jarvis D.; Costanza R.; Hasan S.; Smart J.C.R.; Finisdore J.; Lovelock C.E.; Greenhalgh S.; Marr H.M.; Beck M.W.; Gillies C.L.; Waltham N.J.	Financial incentives for large-scale wetland restoration: Beyond markets to common asset trusts	2021	One Earth
19	Clare S.; Creed I.F.	The Essential Role of Wetland Restoration Practitioners in the Science-Policy-Practice Process	2022	Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution
20	Colten C.E.	Environmental Management in Coastal Louisiana: A Historical Review	2017	Journal of Coastal Research
21	De Steven D.; Gramling J.M.	Diverse characteristics of wetlands restored under the wetlands reserve program in the Southeastern United States	2012	Wetlands
22	Dronova I.	Object-based image analysis in wetland research: A review	2015	Remote Sensing
23	Enu K.B.; Zingraff-Hamed A.; Rahman M.A.; Stringer L.C.; Pauleit S.	Review article: Potential of nature-based solutions to mitigate hydro-meteorological risks in sub-Saharan Africa	2023	Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences
24	Giller P.S.	River restoration: Seeking ecological standards. Editor's introduction	2005	Journal of Applied Ecology
25	González E.; Martínez-Fernández V.; Shafroth P.B.; Sher A.A.; Henry A.L.; Garófano-Gómez V.; Corenblit D.	Regeneration of Salicaceae riparian forests in the Northern Hemisphere: A new framework and management tool	2018	Journal of Environmental Management
26	Gordon B.A.; Dorothy O.; Lenhart C.F.	Nutrient retention in ecologically functional floodplains: A review	2020	Water (Switzerland)
27	Han D.; Yang Y.; Yang Y.; Li K.	Recent advances in wetland degradation research	2012	Shengtai Xuebao/ Acta Ecologica Sinica

No. crt	Authors	Title	Year	Source title
28	Hashisaki S.	Functional wetland restoration: An ecosystem approach	1996	Northwest Science
29	Hovick S.M.; Adams C.R.; Anderson N.O.; Kettenring K.M.	Progress on Mechanisms and Impacts of Wetland Plant Invasions: A Twenty-Year Retrospective Analysis and Priorities for the Next Twenty	2023	Critical Reviews in Plant Sciences
30	Jiang T.-T.; Pan J.-F.; Pu X.-M.; Wang B.; Pan J.-J.	Current status of coastal wetlands in China: Degradation, restoration, and future management	2015	Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science
31	Johnson C.R.; Cave K.	Reclaim the Rouge river	2003	Public Works
32	Kaiser K.; Lorenz S.; Germer S.; Juschus O.; Küster M.; Libra J.; Bens O.; Hüttl R.F.	Late Quaternary evolution of rivers, lakes and peatlands in northeast Germany reflecting past climatic and human impact – an overview; [Die spätquartäre Entwicklung von Flüssen, Seen und Mooren in Nordostdeutschland als Spiegel klimatischer und anthropogener Einflüsse – eine Übersicht]	2012	E and G Quaternary Science Journal
33	Kettenring K.M.; Tarsa E.E.	Need to Seed? Ecological, Genetic, and Evolutionary Keys to Seed-Based Wetland Restoration	2020	Frontiers in Environmental Science
34	Kidd J.G.; Streever B.; Joyce M.R.; Fanter L.H.	Wetland restoration of an exploratory well on Alaska's north slope: A learning experience	2004	Ecological Restoration
35	Kinder K.	Planning by intermediaries: Making cities make nature in Amsterdam	2011	Environment and Planning A
36	Knox R.L.; Wohl E.E.; Morrison R.R.	Levees don't protect, they disconnect: A critical review of how artificial levees impact floodplain functions	2022	Science of the Total Environment
37	Langhans S.D.; Tiegs S.D.; Uehlinger U.; Tockner K.	Environmental heterogeneity controls organic-matter dynamics in river-floodplain ecosystems	2006	Polish Journal of Ecology
38	Lee S.; McCarty G.W.; Lang M.W.; Li X.	Overview of the USDA mid-Atlantic regional wetland conservation effects assessment project	2020	Journal of Soil and Water Conservation
39	Li W.; Changchun S.; Jinming H.; Tao Y.	Response of regeneration diversity of <i>Carex lasiocarpa</i> community to different water levels in Sanjiang Plain, China	2010	Chinese Geographical Science
40	Liang S.; Li H.; Wu H.; Yan B.; Song A.	Microorganisms in coastal wetland sediments: a review on microbial community structure, functional gene, and environmental potential	2023	Frontiers in Microbiology

No. crt	Authors	Title	Year	Source title
41	Liu X.; Wang K.; Zhang G.	Perspectives and policies: Ecological industry substitutes in wetland restoration of the middle Yangtze	2004	Wetlands
42	Ma Z.; Choi C.-Y.; Gan X.; Li J.; Liu Y.; Melville D.S.; Mu T.; Piersma T.; Zhang Z.	Achievements, challenges, and recommendations for waterbird conservation in China's coastal wetlands	2023	Avian Research
43	Maltby E.	The Wetlands Paradigm Shift in Response to Changing Societal Priorities: A Reflective Review	2022	Land
44	Marburger J.E.; Johnson W.E.; Gross T.S.; Douglas D.R.; Di J.	Residual organochlorine pesticides in soils and fish from wetland restoration areas in central Florida, USA	2002	Wetlands
45	McDermott S.; Burdick D.; Grizzle R.; Greene J.	Restoring ecological functions and increasing community awareness of an urban tidal pond using blue mussels	2008	Ecological Restoration
46	McDougall C.	Erosion and the beaches of Negril	2017	Ocean and Coastal Management
47	McGlone M.S.	Postglacial history of New Zealand wetlands and implications for their conservation	2009	New Zealand Journal of Ecology
48	Moomaw W.R.; Chmura G.L.; Davies G.T.; Finlayson C.M.; Middleton B.A.; Natali S.M.; Perry J.E.; Roulet N.; Sutton-Grier A.E.	Wetlands In a Changing Climate: Science, Policy and Management	2018	Wetlands
49	Moreno-Mateos D.; Comin F.A.	Integrating objectives and scales for planning and implementing wetland restoration and creation in agricultural landscapes	2010	Journal of Environmental Management
50	Muehlbauer J.D.; Doyle M.W.; Bernhardt E.S.	Macroinvertebrate community responses to a dewatering disturbance gradient in a restored stream	2011	Hydrology and Earth System Sciences
51	Nakamura K.; Tockner K.; Amano K.	River and wetland restoration: Lessons from Japan	2006	BioScience
52	Nassauer J.I.	Monitoring the success of metropolitan wetland restorations: Cultural sustainability and ecological function	2004	Wetlands
53	Obropta C.C.; Kallin P.L.	The restoration of an urban floodplain in Rahway, New Jersey	2007	Ecological Restoration
54	Otte M.L.; Fang W.-T.; Jiang M.	A Framework for Identifying Reference Wetland Conditions in Highly Altered Landscapes	2021	Wetlands

No. crt	Authors	Title	Year	Source title
55	Paul Kemp G.; McDade E.C.; Day J.W.; Lane R.R.; Dawers N.H.; Day J.N.	Recovery and restoration of Biloxi marsh in the Mississippi River Delta	2021	Water (Switzerland)
56	Peters B.; van Buuren M.; van den Herik K.; Daalder M.; Tempels B.; Rijke J.; Pedroli B.	The Smart Rivers approach: Spatial quality in flood protection and floodplain restoration projects based on river DNA	2021	Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Water
57	Ramchander M.; Rahul K.	Microbial diversity in wetlands of India	2021	Research Journal of Chemistry and Environment
58	Renzi J.J.; He Q.; Silliman B.R.	Harnessing positive species interactions to enhance coastal wetland restoration	2019	Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution
59	Rivera-Monroy V.H.; Lenaker P.; Twilley R.R.; Delaune R.D.; Lindau C.W.; Nuttle W.; Habib E.; Fulweiler R.W.; Castañeda-Moya E.	Denitrification in coastal Louisiana: A spatial assessment and research needs	2010	Journal of Sea Research
60	Rodrigo M.A.	Wetland restoration with hydrophytes: A review	2021	Plants
61	Sapkota Y.; White J.R.	Carbon offset market methodologies applicable for coastal wetland restoration and conservation in the United States: A review	2020	Science of the Total Environment
62	Schaffer B.	Flooding responses and water-use efficiency of subtropical and tropical fruit trees in an environmentally sensitive wetland	1998	Annals of Botany
63	Scott B.; Baldwin A.H.; Ballantine K.; Palmer M.; Yarwood S.	The role of organic amendments in wetland restorations	2020	Restoration Ecology
64	Sheehan L.; Sherwood E.T.; Moyer R.P.; Radabaugh K.R.; Simpson S.	Blue Carbon: an Additional Driver for Restoring and Preserving Ecological Services of Coastal Wetlands in Tampa Bay (Florida, USA)	2019	Wetlands
65	Sherren K.; Ellis K.; Guimond J.A.; Kurylyk B.; LeRoux N.; Lundholm J.; Mallory M.L.; Van Proosdij D.; Walker A.K.; Bowron T.M.; Brazner J.; Kellman L.; Turner B.L., II; Wells E.	Understanding multifunctional bay of fundy dykelands and tidal wetlands using ecosystem services—a baseline	2021	Facets
66	Sims A.; Zhang Y.; Gajaraj S.; Brown P.B.; Hu Z.	Toward the development of microbial indicators for wetland assessment	2013	Water Research
67	Sinks I.A.; Borde A.B.; Diefenderfer H.L.; Karnezis J.P.	Assessment of Methods to Control Invasive Reed Canarygrass (<i>Phalaris arundinacea</i>) in Tidal Freshwater Wetlands	2021	Natural Areas Journal

No. crt	Authors	Title	Year	Source title
68	Skinner M.	Wetland phosphorus dynamics and phosphorus removal potential	2022	Water Environment Research
69	Sloey T.M.; Ellis V.S.; Kettenring K.M.	Using Plant Functional Traits to Inform Wetland Restoration	2023	Wetlands
70	Sparks R.E.; Douglas Blodgett K.; Casper A.F.; Hagy H.M.; Lemke M.J.; Velho L.F.M.; Rodrigues L.C.	Why experiment with success? Opportunities and risks in applying assessment and adaptive management to the Emiquon floodplain restoration project	2017	Hydrobiologia
71	Stokes D.J.; Bulmer R.H.; Lundquist C.J.	Addressing the mismatch between restoration objectives and monitoring needs to support mangrove management	2016	Ocean and Coastal Management
72	Stubbs Q.; Yeo I.-Y.; Lang M.; Townshend J.; Sun L.; Prestegaard K.; Jantz C.	Assessment of Wetland Change on the Delmarva Peninsula from 1984 to 2010	2020	Journal of Coastal Research
73	Sullivan P.L.; Gaiser E.E.; Surratt D.; Rudnick D.T.; Davis S.E.; Sklar F.H.	Wetland ecosystem response to hydrologic restoration and management: The everglades and its urban-Agricultural boundary (FL, USA)	2014	Wetlands
74	Sun Z.; Sun W.; Tong C.; Zeng C.; Yu X.; Mou X.	China's coastal wetlands: Conservation history, implementation efforts, existing issues and strategies for future improvement	2015	Environment International
75	Szuch R.P.; White J.G.; Vepraskas M.J.; Doolittle J.A.	Application of ground penetrating radar to aid restoration planning for a drained carolina BAY	2006	Wetlands
76	Teytelboym A.	Natural capital market design	2019	Oxford Review of Economic Policy
77	Tomer M.D.; Nelson J.A.	Measurements of landscape capacity for water detention and wetland restoration practices can inform watershed planning goals and implementation strategies	2020	Journal of Soil and Water Conservation
78	Turnipseed D.P.; Middleton B.A.	Foreword: Function, classification and management of asian wetlands	2014	Wetlands
79	Turnock D.	Cross-border conservation in East Central Europe: The Danube-Carpathian complex and the contribution of the World Wide Fund for Nature	2001	GeoJournal
80	Vellidis G.; Smith M.C.; Leibowitz S.G.; Ainslie W.B.; Pruitt B.A.	Prioritizing wetland restoration for sediment yield reduction: A conceptual model	2003	Environmental Management

No. crt	Authors	Title	Year	Source title
81	Wantzen K.M.; Alves C.B.M.; Badiane S.D.; Bala R.; Blettler M.; Callisto M.; Cao Y.; Kolb M.; Kondolf G.M.; Leite M.F.; Macedo D.R.; Mahdi O.; Neves M.; Peralta M.E.; Rotgé V.; Rueda-Delgado G.; Scharager A.; Serra-Llobet A.; Yengué J.-L.; Zingraff-Hamed A.	Urban stream and wetland restoration in the global south—a DPSIR analysis	2019	Sustainability (Switzerland)
82	Weinstein M.P.; Litvin S.Y.	Macro-Restoration of Tidal Wetlands: A Whole Estuary Approach	2016	Ecological Restoration
83	White J.S.; Bayley S.E.	Restoration of a Canadian prairie wetland with agricultural and municipal wastewater	1999	Environmental Management
84	Xu S.; Liu X.; Li X.; Tian C.	Soil organic carbon changes following wetland restoration: A global meta-analysis	2019	Geoderma
85	Yang T.; He Q.; Jiang J.; Sheng L.; Jiang H.; He C.	Impact of Water Table on Methane Emission Dynamics in Terrestrial Wetlands and Implications on Strategies for Wetland Management and Restoration	2022	Wetlands
86	Yang W.; Sun T.; Yang Z.	Does the implementation of environmental flows improve wetland ecosystem services and biodiversity? A literature review	2016	Restoration Ecology
87	Young P.	The 'new science' of wetland restoration	1996	Environmental Science and Technology
88	Yu S.; Cui B.; Xie T.; Wang Q.; Yan J.; Ning Z.	Research progress and development trend of coastal wetland restoration in greater bay areas	2022	Watershed Ecology and the Environment
89	Yuguda T.K.; Leng Z.; Wu Y.; Jia H.; Zhang S.; Dai Z.; Li J.; Du D.	Consequences of Coastal Wetlands Reclamation and the Need for Integrating Impact Assessment of Invasive Alien Plants Species and Coastal Armoring in Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)	2022	International Journal of Environmental Research
90	Zak D.; Hupfer M.; Cabezas A.; Jurasinski G.; Audet J.; Kleeberg A.; McInnes R.; Kristiansen S.M.; Petersen R.J.; Liu H.; Goldhammer T.	Sulphate in freshwater ecosystems: A review of sources, biogeochemical cycles, ecotoxicological effects and bioremediation	2021	Earth-Science Reviews
91	Zambrano L.; Rivas M.I.; Uriel-Sumano C.; Rojas-Villaseñor R.; Rubio M.; Mena H.; Vázquez-Mendoza D.L.; Tovar-Garza A.	Adapting wetland restoration practices in Urban areas: Perspectives from Xochimilco in Mexico City	2020	Ecological Restoration
92	Zedler J.B.	Progress in wetland restoration ecology	2000	Trends in Ecology and Evolution

No. crt	Authors	Title	Year	Source title
93	Zentner J.; Glaspy J.; Schenk D.	Wetland and riparian woodland restoration costs	2003	Ecological Restoration
94	Zhao Q.; Bai J.; Huang L.; Gu B.; Lu Q.; Gao Z.	A review of methodologies and success indicators for coastal wetland restoration	2016	Ecological Indicators

APPENDIX B RESTORATION PROJECT ASSESSMENT SURVEY

1. Site name
2. Beneficiary name
3. Country
4. Geographical coordinates (latitude/ longitude) – decimal degrees. Provide coordinates of the approximate centre of the site
5. Project name and project reference/ code
6. Year(s) of restoration project. If possible, specify the duration of the planning phase and the implementation phase.
7. Surface of the restored area (in hectares)
8. Project costs (in euros). If possible, please delineate between the costs in the planning phase and implementation phase.
9. Designation and protection status. (Select all that apply)
 - a. Ramsar site
 - b. UNESCO World Heritage Site
 - c. National Park
 - d. Natural Park
 - e. SPA
 - f. SCI
 - g. Biosphere Reserve
 - h. Other. Please specify: _____
10. Please upload up to 3 photos.
11. Please upload the restoration site map. (shapefile; please upload a zip archive)
12. Please upload a map with the larger area of social-ecological interest (shapefile; please upload a zip archive)
13. Provide URLs: project website and/or links to other documents (technical reports, scientific papers etc.)
14. Data provider (name of person filling in this survey)
15. Data provider email (shall not be made public)

16. What was/were the main objectives of the restoration project? Select all that apply.

- a. Species restoration
- b. Habitat and/or ecosystem recovery
- c. Landscape reconstruction
- d. Hydromorphology
- e. Water quality
- f. Other. Please specify: _____

17. Indicators used before restoration (planning phase). Please select all that apply

- a. Species composition
 - i. Species abundance
 - ii. Species occurrence
 - iii. Target species occurrence
- b. Structural diversity
 - i. Density/ Abundance
 - ii. Functional composition
 - iii. Habitat distribution
 - iv. Vegetation cover
- c. Physical conditions
 - i. Bank characteristics
 - ii. Channel characteristics
 - iii. Light availability
 - iv. Microclimate
 - v. Soil/ sediment characteristics
 - vi. Water chemical characteristics
 - vii. Water physical characteristics
- d. Ecosystem functioning
 - i. Carbon fluxes
 - ii. Erosion

- iii. Productivity
- iv. Sedimentation
- e. Species traits
 - i. Habitat quality
 - ii. Population density
 - iii. Population structure

18. Indicators used after restoration (monitoring phase). Please select all that apply

- a. Species composition
 - i. Species abundance
 - ii. Species occurrence
 - iii. Target species occurrence
- b. Structural diversity
 - i. Density/ Abundance
 - ii. Functional composition
 - iii. Habitat distribution
 - iv. Vegetation cover
- c. Physical conditions
 - i. Bank characteristics
 - ii. Channel characteristics
 - iii. Light availability
 - iv. Microclimate
 - v. Soil/ sediment characteristics
 - vi. Water chemical characteristics
 - vii. Water physical characteristics
- d. Ecosystem functioning
 - i. Carbon fluxes
 - ii. Erosion
 - iii. Productivity

- iv. Sedimentation
- e. Species traits
 - i. Habitat quality
 - ii. Population density
 - iii. Population structure

19. Specify landscape type/ landcover before restoration (EUNIS level 1):

- a. Marine habitats
- b. Coastal habitats
- c. Surface standing waters (inland surface water)
- d. Surface running waters (inland surface water)
- e. Littoral zone of inland surface waterbodies (inland surface water)
- f. Mires, bogs and fens
- g. Grasslands and lands dominated by forbs, mosses and lichens
- h. Heathland, scrub and tundra
- i. Woodland forest and other wooded land
- j. Inland unvegetated or sparsely vegetated habitats
- k. Regularly or recently cultivated agricultural, horticultural and domestic habitats
- l. Constructed, industrial and other artificial habitats
- m. Habitat complexes

20. Specify landscape type/ landcover post- restoration (EUNIS level 1):

- a. Marine habitats
- b. Coastal habitats
- c. Surface standing waters (inland surface water)
- d. Surface running waters (inland surface water)
- e. Littoral zone of inland surface waterbodies (inland surface water)
- f. Mires, bogs and fens
- g. Grasslands and lands dominated by forbs, mosses and lichens

- h. Heathland, scrub and tundra
 - i. Woodland forest and other wooded land
 - j. Inland unvegetated or sparsely vegetated habitats
 - k. Regularly or recently cultivated agricultural, horticultural and domestic habitats
 - l. Constructed, industrial and other artificial habitats
 - m. Habitat complexes
21. Please specify the restoration measures or techniques used in your project. E.g. restoring dams or levees, reintroducing native plants, controlling invasive species, rerouting channels etc.
22. Which type(s) of ecosystem services displayed noticeable increases post-restoration? Please select all that apply.
- a. Provisioning
 - b. Regulating
 - c. Supporting
 - d. Cultural
23. What types of actors were involved in restoration planning process? Please specify all types of actors involved. E.g.: national and or/local decision-makers, sectoral authorities, researchers, local community representatives, NGOs etc.
24. How were civil society/ local communities/ businesses and other affected stakeholders engaged in decision-making during the restoration process? Select all that apply.
- a. Community meetings and workshops
 - b. Surveys and questionnaires
 - c. Focus groups
 - d. Public hearings
 - e. Community advisory boards
 - f. Participatory mapping exercises
 - g. Education and outreach programs
 - h. Feedback mechanisms such as hotline numbers or online platforms
 - i. Other. Please specify: _____

25. In what phases of the restoration process were civil society/ local communities/ businesses and other affected stakeholder engaged? Select all that apply.
- Planning phase
 - Implementation phase
 - Post-restoration phase
26. If local and traditional ecological knowledge (Knowledge and insights acquired through extensive observation of an area or a species. This may include knowledge passed down in an oral tradition or shared among users of a resource.) has been incorporated into the restoration process, please indicate how. Select all that apply.
- Habitat preference
 - Seasonal variability and phenology
 - Land use history and traditional management practises
 - Ecological interactions
 - Indicators of environmental change
 - Traditional governance systems
 - Other. Please specify: _____
27. Were any educational programs developed to build community capacity and/ or support wetland restoration project? Yes / no
28. Has social acceptance been assessed for your restoration project? Select all that apply
- Public acceptance has been assessed during the planning phase.
 - Public acceptance has been assessed post-restoration.
 - Stakeholder group acceptance has been assessed during the planning phase.
 - Stakeholder group acceptance has been assessed post-restoration.
29. What property rights system governs the restoration area? Please specify if there were any regulations dealing with property rights that hampered the restoration process. The property rights system refers to the legal framework governing ownership, usage, access rights and management of land and water resources within the area targeted for restoration. This includes regulations, agreements, and policies dictating who owns the land, what activities are permitted or prohibited, and how stakeholders interact regarding wetland restoration efforts.
30. What were the obstacles that arose during any of the restoration process phases? (E.g.: unclear legal framework, legal framework had to be updated, insufficient technical

capacity, insufficient local community not in favour, interest group strong lobby, obtaining licenses etc.)

31. What special governance tools/ mechanisms (e.g. expropriation, acquisition) have you used in your restoration project that enabled/simplified the usage of land for restoration actions? Please name what specific tools and mechanisms are available in your country for the same purpose.
32. Are there any specific information or conditions regarding collaboration with authorities during the planning process that you would like to emphasize?
33. Are there different approval procedures in your country concerning wetland restorations? If yes, what are the criteria (e.g. type of measures, size of the area to be restored) to select the right procedure?
34. Which sectoral authorities have been involved within the (different) procedure(s) in your restoration project?
35. Are climate change projections utilised to inform the long-term management of the restored wetland? Yes/ No
36. What initiatives were undertaken to raise awareness about wetland restoration? E.g.: scientific papers, podcasts, radio, TV, social media engagement, events, local festivals etc.
37. Type of financial support. Select all that apply.
 - a. Government grants and funding
 - b. International funding organisations
 - c. NGO funding
 - d. Private foundations and philanthropy
 - e. Corporate sponsorship and CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility)
 - f. Public-private partnership
 - g. Crowdfunding and community fundraising
 - h. Carbon offsets and environmental markets
 - i. Payments for Ecosystem Services
 - j. Other. Please specify: _____
38. Please provide a general overview of funding options in your country.
39. If funding mechanisms are in place post-restoration (after the implementation phase), what types of activities are being financed? E.g.: ecological monitoring, maintenance work, communications and outreach, local capacity building, etc."

40. Have economic benefits been assessed post-restoration? Select all that apply.
- Local economy
 - Economic costs vs benefits
 - Ecosystem services
 - Resources for local livelihoods
 - Other. Please specify: _____
41. Please share any relevant findings regarding the project's contribution to the local economy. E.g., restoring the Carasuhat area in the Danube Delta in Romania directly reduced by 50% the time needed for fishers and tourist transport operators to reach the fishing and birdwatching areas. This also translates into halving fuel consumption. Official data show an increase in tourists, a rise in the number of tourism-related businesses, and an increase in the profit generated by tourism activities.
42. How has the area that underwent restoration shown its ability to withstand and recover from environmental pressures induced by climate change after the restoration process? For example, have there been observable instances of the ecosystem recovering following severe climate events?"
43. Were there any adjustments or modifications made to the management plans in response to observed climate impacts? Yes / No
44. Please elaborate on any additional points, specific situations, conditions, or procedures that you deem noteworthy.